

On the Huggins Constants for Methyl Methacrylate-Acrylonitrile Random Copolymers

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This paper considers random copolymers of methyl methacrylate with acrylonitrile. It describes an assessment of solvent power for polymers on the basis of the Huggins constant k' , and a comparison is made with other criteria of solvent power.

IN an earlier study dealing with the effect of composition on the Huggins constant, k' for methyl methacrylate acrylonitrile random copolymers¹, it was concluded that the value of k' is dependent strongly both on the composition of the copolymer as well as the nature of the solvent. Whereas, the former study dealt with our preliminary viscosity experiments on unfractionated copolymers, the present study refers to detailed studies on the Huggins constant for fractionated copolymers. With the availability of the data on the various solution properties of these copolymers²⁻⁵, viz., Mark-Houwink Exponent, a , copolymer-solvent interaction parameter χ_1 , it is also intended to see whether k' could be considered as a measure of the solvent power for the copolymer systems.

Experimental

The copolymers were prepared by solution polymerization method and fractionated by fractional precipitation method. The details of preparation, criteria for selection of various solvent-nonsolvent

pairs for fractionation etc. have been reported earlier⁶. The data on light scattering and viscosity measurements, and evaluation of various parameters, such as Mark-Houwink constants, short range and long range interaction parameters, have been reported elsewhere²⁻⁵.

Results and Discussion

Huggins constant, is evaluated from the slope of $\frac{\eta_{SP}}{C}$ vs C . plots, in accordance with following equation :

$$\eta_{SP}/C = [\eta] + k' [\eta]^2 C$$

The values of k' were found for the copolymer fractions in methyl ethylketone (MEK), acetonitrile (MeCN), dimethyl formamide (DMF), γ -butyrolactone (γ -BL) at 30°, 45° and 60°, from the usual Huggins plots (See Tables 1-4). The data for the evaluation of k' were treated by the least square method⁵.

TABLE 1—HUGGINS CONSTANTS, FOR MA1 (COMPOSITION : 0.289 M.F. OF AN)

Fraction	$\bar{M}_w \times 10^{-5}$	MEK	MeCN	DMF			γ -BL		
		30°	30°	30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°
MA111	79.03	0.51	0.52	0.35	0.33	0.36	0.39	0.37	0.29
MA121	47.72	0.53	0.55	0.33	0.36	0.31	0.28	0.35	0.16
MA122	42.95	0.54	0.53	0.36	0.38	0.39	0.31	0.35	0.35
MA14	31.61	0.60	0.60	0.41	0.39	0.41	0.40	0.38	0.33
MA15	23.71	0.48	0.47	0.37	0.34	0.30	0.25	0.36	0.36
MA17	8.38	0.43	0.46	0.39	0.22	0.44	0.43	0.90	0.32

TABLE 2—HUGGINS CONSTANTS FOR MA2 (COMPOSITION : 0.415 M.F. OF AN)

Fraction	$\bar{M}_w \times 10^{-5}$	MEK	MeCN	DMF			γ -BL		
		30°	30°	30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°
MA211	25.12	0.82	0.52	0.12	0.17	0.19	0.45	0.38	0.40
MA24	9.30	0.58	0.45	0.11	0.08	0.05	0.42	0.54	0.35
MA212	9.18	0.76	0.60	0.05	0.31	0.34	0.53	0.48	0.46
MA25	6.33	0.57	0.50	-0.12	0.28	0.25	0.88	0.85	0.52
MA27	1.65	0.43	0.35	-0.31	0.30	-0.40	0.42	0.36	0.27

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TABLE 3—HUGGINS CONSTANTS FOR MA3 (COMPOSITION : 0.566 M.F. OF AN)^a

Fraction	$\bar{M}_w \times 10^{-5}$	MEK 30°	MeCN 30°	DMF			γ -BL		
				30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°
				MA311	12.95	0.51	0.45	0.48	0.46
MA321	9.99	0.67	0.53	0.38	0.43	0.23	0.31	0.31	0.29
MA33	6.99	0.71	0.52	0.58	0.53	0.49	0.25	0.32	0.37
MA34	6.30	0.82	0.60	0.34	0.38	0.36	0.22	0.26	0.21
MA35	5.01	0.63	0.48	0.36	0.40	0.29	0.38	0.38	0.36

TABLE 4—HUGGINS CONSTANTS, k' FOR MA4 (COMPOSITION : 0.657 M.F. OF AN)

Fraction	$\bar{M}_w \times 10^{-5}$	MeCN 30°	DMF			γ -BL		
			30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°
			MA421	8.99	0.73	0.41	0.46	0.47
MA431	6.42	0.68	0.44	0.40	0.45	0.42	0.38	0.33
MA433	4.63	0.82	0.56	0.52	0.49	0.58	0.40	0.41
MA45	3.17	0.79	0.54	0.48	0.53	0.60	0.39	0.43
MA46	2.48	0.43	0.16	0.19	0.28	0.35	0.37	0.26

It is seen that k' depends on molecular weight, solvent and temperature for a particular composition of copolymer. The dependence of k' on the molecular weight is contrary to the observations made by Huggins⁷, that k' is to be independent of molecular weight, in view of the fact that these copolymers were fractionated with respect to molecular weight alone⁶. For the copolymer fractions of similar molecular weight, the solvent power for various solvents has been classified, based on k' values (Table 5).

It is obvious that except for MA2, the solvent power for other copolymers is $\text{MEK} < \text{MeCN} < \text{DMF} < \gamma\text{-BL}$. The effect of composition on this order is not noticed. It is to be noted that, whereas MEK and MeCN are nonsolvents for one or both parent homopolymers, DMF & γ -BL are solvents for both the parent homopolymers. The effect of temperature on k' is not of a uniform nature.

From the present study, it follows that k' could be taken as a fairly accurate parameter for

TABLE 5—SOLVENT POWERS OF VARIOUS SOLVENTS, BASED ON THE PARAMETERS k' , a , B AND χ_1 :

	MA1	MA2	MA3	MA4
k'	1 < 2 < 3 < 4	1 < 2 < 4 < 3	1 < 2 < 3 < 4	2 < 3 < 4
a	1 < 2 < 3 < 4	3 < 4 < 1 < 2	1 < 3 < 4 < 2	2 < 3 < 4
B	1 < 2 < 3 < 4	1 < 4 < 2 < 3	1 < 2 < 3 < 4	2 < 3 < 4
χ_1	2 < 1 < 3 < 4	2 < 1 < 4 < 3	2 < 1 < 3 < 4	2 < 3 < 4

1 = MEK ; 2 = MeCN ; 3 = DMF ; 4 = γ -BL.

Table 5 also includes the solvent power of the same set of solvents based on a , B and χ_1 ²⁻⁵. It is important to emphasize that, whereas B and χ_1 (related to B through molal volume of the solvent) are measures of long range interactions between polymer and solvent when the chain extension occurs through polymer-solvent interactions alone, k' and a depict the overall picture of the various kinds of interactions.

In our studies on the dilute solution properties of these copolymers²⁻⁵, it was concluded that these copolymers assume large extension mainly due to short range interactions, rather than long range interactions. Further, it was also concluded that Stockmayer-Fixman equations or variants thereof may have to be modified for such polar systems. Therefore, it appears that B and χ_1 could be considered as of limited and qualitative significance only.

From Table 5, the solvent power of various solvents are as follows :

MEK \leq MeCN $<$ DMF $<$ γ -BL : MA1
 MEK $<$ MeCN \leq γ -BL $<$ DMF : MA2
 MEK $<$ MeCN \leq DMF $<$ γ -BL : MA3
 MeCN $<$ DMF $<$ γ -BL : MA4

determining the solvent power of various solvents. The evaluation of k' is simple and does not involve the handling of delicate instruments such as Light Scattering Photometers or Osmometers.

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